

ASIDE

DIGITAL NEEDS FOR SOCIAL SERVICES

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DIGITAL NEED FOR SOCIAL SERVICES

Responsible: Javier SANCHEZ GARCIA - EuroFUE-UJI

Introduction

The social services sector has suffered major financial cuts in recent years, yet this sector is facing increasing economic needs in all European countries. In contrast, we are currently seeing a reduction in public budgets, yet the world's population is ageing. In this scenario, the digitalisation of social services can help to do more with fewer resources. The digitisation of social services has the potential to improve the quality of care and life of people who use these social services.

The increasing role of technology in social services may take many forms, such as the use of artificial intelligence, case management systems, technology driven services, or assistive technology. These technological advancements can help improve social services planning, management and delivery, but it is also important to understand the challenges digitalisation raises, such as the lack of knowledge about new technologies, its cost and how to ensure privacy and security are protected.

The process of digitisation of social services can be analysed from various points of view:

- use of artificial intelligence,
- case management systems,
- technology driven services or assistive technology.

The planning, management and delivery of social services can be greatly enhanced by the application of these digital technologies. However, it is important to analyse in depth the challenges posed by digitization, such as the lack of knowledge of new technologies, their cost and how to ensure privacy and security protection.

In the specific case of adult education, information and communication technologies (ICT) and digital education processes for this segment of the population cannot be ignored. From a modern perspective of adult education, it is moving away from the encyclopaedism of teaching in favour of combining traditional teaching methods with the use of information and communication technology, with active group work methods, workshops, training and methods of moderation.

At present, adult education is not the educator's "one right" and the only effective method of education. On the contrary, the educator takes the personal interests, experience and internal motivation of adults as a reference for learning. By bringing forth a positive and supportive learning environment, he or she motivates an adult student to learn independently, inspires and strengthens the learning process. In this way, adult learners independently manage the learning and development process, strengthen self-esteem and self-assessment.

Because of digitisation and the application of ICT in social services focused on adults, the education of this target group has to face new challenges related to professional and

personal aspects. The challenge is focused on the integration of digital skills acquired by adults with their professional and personal environment.

In today's digital environment, it is essential for adults to strengthen their education adapted to the local conditions of everyone, but with a global perspective.

In relation to adult educators, their ICT skills are essential for the promotion of ICT use among adults in various real-life situations.

The aim of this report is to examine in the four countries involved in the project (Turkey, Poland, Czech Republic and Spain) the digital needs of social services in each country.

Javier SANCHEZ GARCIA

1. Digital need for social services: The Spanish case

Responsible: Javier SANCHEZ GARCIA - EuroFUE-UJI

In Spain, the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation is responsible for proposing and implementing economic policy and reforms to improve competitiveness, telecommunications and the information society. This Ministry is also responsible for proposing and executing the Government's policy for digital transformation and the development and promotion of artificial intelligence. This Ministry is structured in the following higher entities:

- a. State Secretariat for the Economy and Business Support.
- b. State Secretariat for Digitalization and Artificial Intelligence**
- c. State Secretariat for Telecommunications and Digital Infrastructure.

On the other hand, the Ministry of Social Rights and 2030 Agenda is responsible for social services. This ministry carries out the proposal and execution of the Government's policy in the areas of social welfare, family, child protection, cohesion and care of dependent or disabled persons, youth, as well as animal protection. In addition, the Ministry of Social Rights and Agenda is responsible for proposing and executing the Government's policy on promoting 2030 the implementation of the United Nations 2030 Agenda.

This Ministry is structured in the following higher entities:

- a. State Secretariat for Social Rights.**
- b. State Secretariat for 2030 Agenda.

This means that in Spain, two secretariats of state must agree to analyse the needs and subsequent development of the digitalisation of social services.

Having seen the reference framework on digitisation and social services in Spain, the study focuses on the digital needs of social services in Spain. To this end, the study by the CEOE (entrepreneur's confederation) regarding the digitalization of Spanish society is taken as a reference. As a general objective it is proposed that through digital technologies it can be achieved: (1) maximise the efficiency and quality levels of social services and (2) provide an effective response to citizens' demands for social services. Digital technologies are the great ally of social services.

In order to achieve the overall objective, there are several needs relating to the digitisation of social services:

1. Define a digital social services strategy led by the Ministry of Social Rights and 2030 Agenda. To this end, it is necessary to provide the system with an appropriate governance structure to address the process of digitalisation of social services, as well as to allocate specific funds for the development of the strategy with a defined time horizon.
2. Make effective the right of the patient to access social services and information by digital means (extension of the application of Law 11/2007 to the health field so that digital social services are a right of citizens).
3. Adopt the necessary measures that promote, respecting the rights of users, the exploitation of the information of the social services system for the purpose of

improving the quality, efficiency, planning, management, evaluation of social services, research, development and innovation. Recognise a legitimate interest in the re-use of data for research purposes, with no need to seek consent again, in line with the provisions of the data protection section.

4. Exploiting Big Data in the social services environment to develop and foster the use of intelligent cognitive systems. This exploitation of data should be accessible to social services professionals. To this end, it is necessary to advance in the secondary use of data in accordance with the legality of data protection.
5. Implement decision support tools in social services. This tool should be indicative and based on the best practices used by social services. It could take as a reference the systems based on cognitive technologies used in health.
6. Develop analytical tools of population information that allow the identification of risk factors and the determination of patterns to define and implement preventive measures.
7. Make the social services system more transparent and measure the impact and evolution of digital social services.
8. Create an information exchange system that includes the key aspects for the management of social services. The aim would be to create a standardised digital data repository accessible to all actors involved in social services. This system should be available at any time and from anywhere.
9. Develop digital tools that favour the empowerment of users of social services, such as access by citizens to their digital records, by means of electronic ID cards or other appropriate identification systems.
10. Social services should be aware of and apply existing laws on the development of apps.
11. Implement new indicators that focus on the value of results in social services and not only on process, structure or cost indicators.

The following are actions carried out in Spain to promote the digitalisation of social services.

1. **Barcelona Provincial Council organizes a course on digitalization in social services.** This course was aimed at people in the social field (professionals, staff of entities, university students, etc.). The objective was to present the current models and trends in digitalization of organizations that offer social services. It also showed the ICT tools to improve the efficiency of the entities related to social services and to optimize the time of the professionals working in them.

The points discussed during the course have been:

- use of online services to be able to collaboratively edit documents, share them securely,
- cloud storage,
- image and multimedia file editing,
- productivity, etc.

- 2. Regional Ministry of Equality, Social Policies and Conciliation of the Junta de Andalucía has invested 12 million to digitalize social services and speed up their provision.** This project favours the continuity of care within the Andalusian public system through the application of information and communication technologies. In this way, the Single Electronic Social History (HSUE) will collect all the relevant information on the needs of care, planning, monitoring and evaluation of the Social Intervention Project. Approximately 500,000 users of Andalusian social services will have a Single Electronic Social History by the end of the project, so that at least 30% of the administrative procedures of the social services will have been digitised. This project is a response to the commitment of Law 9/2016 on Social Services in Andalusia to intersectionality, to the coordination between social services, health and other systems of social protection, employment, housing, justice, to solve the problems of citizenship.

2. Digital need for social services: The Polish case

Responsible: Renata OCHOA-DADERSKA, Zofia GRÓDEK-SZOSTAK, Luis OCHOA SIGUENCIA, Anna SZELAĞ-SIKORA, Agnieszka CHEĆCIŃSKA KOPIEC, Jakub SIKORA, Marcin NIEMIEC - Instytut Badań i Innowacji w Edukacji [INBIE]

In Poland, over 9 million people aged 50+ are digitally excluded, which in practice means that they do not have access to electronic services, Internet resources and work tools. Others, although they have access to the Internet, rarely use it. Digital competence of adult Poles processing to the lowest in Europe. It is a real civilization catastrophe that costs Poland 24 billion zlotys annually (PwC, 2013), reducing the quality of life of a quarter of our country.

The study clearly shows how important it is to inspire and support activities leading to universal digital education of adults (especially over the age of 50), dissemination of e-competences and effective use of digital technologies in everyday life and at work.

Social innovations also apply to specific social services or services which attempt to use or apply more technology¹. An example of an innovative social service that is not systemically present in Poland is the "One Button" service. It is available in the Scandinavian countries, Spain, Italy and Great Britain. It consists in the fact that sick people, lonely, disabled, unaccompanied, infirm receive a special digital device, permanently installed on their body in the form of a large electronic button. In the case of malaise, fainting or sudden illness (or for other reasons), after pressing the button, an electronic signal is sent to the operator, who is subject to local sanitary and emergency services. A public or private operator sends an ambulance or paramedic immediately, who are usually non-public subcontractors for this service. The system is supported by the Global Positioning System [GPS²] so as to quickly track the victim³.

"One counter / window" for entrepreneurs

From March 31, 2009, the possibility of registering business activity in the so-called "One window". This means that everyone who wants to start a company submits one application CEIDG-1 to the Commune / City Office in accordance with their place of residence. Business registration, change of data or its liquidation are not subject to any stamp duty.

"One counter" is a facilitation for entrepreneurs (and thus also associations and foundations conducting business activity), which was introduced by the Act of 19 December 2008 amending the Act on freedom of economic activity and amending certain other acts. The

¹ Grewiński M. [2009], Wielosektorowa polityka społeczna – o przeobrażeniach państwa opiekuńczego, Warszawa, Wydawnictwo WSP TWP Google Scholar

² GPS Stands for "Global Positioning System. GPS is a satellite navigation system used to determine the ground position of an object

³ <https://przedsiębiorstwo.waw.pl/resources/html/article/details?id=174078&language=pl>

facilitation was to speed up the possibility of starting operations and protect against visits to many offices.

It consisted in the fact that the organization - entrepreneur, submitting to the "Entry to the National Court Register [KRS]" application for registration or notification of any changes, immediately submitted forms to other offices: Social Security [ZUS], tax office [US] and office statistical (REGON). After entering the organization or its changes into the register, the National Court Register (KRS) sent them via post to other offices.

After the change of regulations, since December 2014, the "one stop shop" principle applies not only to entrepreneurs, but also to organizations that do not run a business. The flow of information between the registry court and offices has been significantly improved (thanks to the ICT system), and organizations do not have to fill out a number of additional forms unnecessarily. Offices, such as the tax or statistical office, collect most information about the organization from KRS forms.

Regional Warning System

The Regional Warning System (RSO) is a free service that allows you to notify citizens about threats. The information is provided by the RSO Mobile Application, MUX-3 terrestrial digital multiplex programs and posted on the websites of provincial offices.

RSO also has an educational role. The system includes guides on, among others how to give first aid or how to behave during a storm, flood or terrorist attack.

Thanks to cooperation with the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management in RSO, meteorological and hydrological warnings (including a map showing the state of waters on the most important water gauges of Polish rivers) are placed. In addition, the system also contains other warnings, e.g. traffic.

National Map of Security Risks

The National Safety Threat Map is an interactive tool that lets you familiarize yourself with the most important information about safety and threats at your location. The map also helps to identify places where local services should pay special attention. The police verify threat signals and, if the information is true, take appropriate action.

Citizens most often report the threats that are most burdensome at their place of residence. These include: incorrect parking, exceeding the speed limit, drinking alcohol in unauthorized places, improper road infrastructure, use of intoxicants or poor organization of road traffic. After confirming the police officers, they really help in solving the problem. For example, in the event of a bad traffic organization that threatens safety, they ask the road administrator to change the traffic organization at this place.

Social security (insurance and benefits)

- a. **ZUS Electronic Services Platform** - provides ZUS e-services, including:
 - allows all clients to check the data saved on an individual account at ZUS, track the status of their cases and receive e-mail or SMS notifications,
 - booking a visit to the ZUS unit,
 - the insured allows checking, among others account balance, insurance information for which it was reported, and the basis for calculating premiums,
 - beneficiaries can check, among others information on benefits awarded and paid out (pensions, disability and benefits),
 - for premium payers, it allows checking due premiums and deposits, information on persons reported for insurance, and also provides the ePłatnik application, thanks to which, through the pue.zus.pl portal, you can register persons for insurance and settle premiums.
 - receiving sick leave electronically by employers (e-ZLA) - a service available from January 2016.
- b. **empatia.mpips.gov.pl** website - provides information on social benefits and the possibility of submitting some applications online, including:
 - applications for family benefits and maintenance,
 - applications for social assistance,
 - applications for social assistance for another person / family,
 - applications for a certificate of assistance,
 - motions regarding changes in the repayment of receivables / payments,
 - e-registration of rehabilitation stays,
 - searching and browsing entities entered in the Register of Rehabilitation Camp Organizers,
 - e-registration of nurseries and children's clubs,
 - searching and browsing of entities entered into the Register of Nurseries and Children's Clubs

Integrated POL-on network

“2018 EUNIS Elite Award for the POL-on system for the best solution in Europe in the field of information systems on higher education”

This is the most comprehensive data repository on Polish science and higher education. Nearly 40 modules were identified in it. It is the largest public system operating from the point of view of the scope of collected data.

First of all, the data collected in the system is used by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education to shape policy based on evidence. Its operation and scope of the collected data, as well as its role in the area of state information systems, are defined by relevant laws and regulations.

The recipients of the data, in addition to the Ministry of Science and Higher Education, are other government agencies, e.g. the Central Statistical Office, the Central Commission for Degrees and Titles, the National Centre for Research and Development, and the National

Science Centre. The basic goal of the system is a real impact on the effective spending of public funds for science and education. The POL-on system has facilitated many reporting obligations for universities by enabling remote reporting.

Thanks to advanced artificial intelligence algorithms, the system investigates various types of violations and trends, which gives the possibility to track events and verify them in real time based on big data sets. A certain range of information collected in the system is made publicly available.

3. Digital need for social services: The Czech Republic case

Responsible: Emil VELINOV – ITC International

Regardless of our intentions, digitization penetrates into all areas of daily life. Whether it is the economic sphere, business sector or public or private spheres. The society and the institutions wish that both the Czech Republic and EU would manage successfully to do their best to motivate the development of digital technologies and help where it is needed. Instead of feeling threatened with digitization and development of technologies, the public and private institutions rather focus on challenges that await us in connection with the transformations of society. The public and private institutions in Czechia are putting efforts to modernize and reform the education, introducing of new elements into lifelong learning and continuous courses and training. Therefore, at the moment is crucial for individuals to focus on acquiring relevant skills, whether it be digital literacy, soft skills, or the support of creative sectors and crafts, i.e. the areas, where robots cannot replace human creative activities.

In the recent years there are numerous of innovations, which have been made in the area of digital tools development for social services. For example, the so-called “Klicenka”, which is a key ID chip designed to identify the location and basic health status of elder people in the Czech Republic has been emerging. This digital product and the services related to it are promoted to several Czech regions, where private companies, start-ups and municipalities are trying to develop practical and handy digital tools for variety of social services. This is triggered by increasing number of older people and increased cooperation between the public and private sectors in terms of creating added value social services for kids and adults.

Another successful project so far in digital education for seniors is the project called Seniors Communicate Program, organized throughout the whole Czech Republic under the patronage of the Livia and Václav Klaus Foundation. The project is implemented at 7 branches of Czech Saving Bank branches in Prague, Brno, Plsen, Kladno, Liberec, Usti 13nd Labem and Hradec Kralove and some other selected organizations that help seniors. The initiative involves education in modern communication technologies, specifically a three-day course focused on learning mobile technologies – with tablets, smart or touch phones and laptops for 10 participants. The course lasts 12 hours over the 3 days in total. Participants bring their own devices (tablets or smartphones).

The main goal of the initiative is to teach participants the basics, to recommend some applications to them and to warn them before possible threats. Also, individual counselling focused on tablets, smartphones or laptops and related services. The individual counselling takes place during Thursdays, between 9 am and 5 pm. The target is to help the participants correctly set up their devices, help them to add or to remove different apps, and advise them on internet or mobile banking (DigiCoalition, 2020).

These are only few examples of developing and providing digital services for kids, adults, seniors and students in the Czech Republic as numerous of NGOs, universities, schools and municipalities are trying to enhance the latest technologies and digital platforms to enable more comfort life and to support especially the seniors to learn digital skills and to

keep them informed in the globalized world. Surely, there is a bigger need to develop and elaborate further digital tools for social services in the Czech Republic as still many seniors and other social groups have the big need of services for their lives.⁴

⁴ Online source accessed [29-03-2020] available at www.digikoalice.cz

4. Digital need for social services: The Turkish case

Responsible: Yeliz NUR AKARÇAY, Sarıcam Halk Eğitimi Merkezi Müdürlüğü

Information and communication technologies that develop at an unprecedented pace create changes not only in economic and social life, but also it leads to new chances and opportunities for individuals, institutions and states.

The 2016-2019 National eGovernment Strategy and Action Plan was Turkey's first comprehensive national eGovernment Strategy and Action Plan. It coordinates different studies concerning the structuring of eGovernment with a holistic approach, taking Turkey's specific conditions, new technological developments and global trends into account. It is compatible with the National Development Plan and Information Society Strategy. The 2016-2019 National eGovernment Strategy and Action Plan aimed to provide the acceleration needed to guide Turkey's digital transformation and achieve social, economic and environmental development. In the new term, eGovernment will be more Integrated, Technological, Participatory, Innovative and Qualified with its focus on being an efficient eGovernment Ecosystem, with a more competent and agile position as the enabler of transition to an information society and sustainable development. With the implementation of the eGovernment Strategy and Action Plan, the objective was to develop the necessary capacity in line with Turkey's 2023 vision and to create an elevating effect for the welfare of the country. In line with this objective, the vision of the 2016-2019 National eGovernment Strategy and Action Plan was defined as 'Improving the quality of life for society with efficient eGovernment'.

Four strategic aims, 13 objectives and 43 actions were determined in line with the vision of 2016-2019 National eGovernment Strategy and Action Plan. The following strategic aims were determined to achieve the vision an eGovernment ecosystem:

- Strategic Aim 1: Ensuring Efficiency and Sustainability of the eGovernment Ecosystem;
- Strategic Aim 2: Implementing Common Systems for Infrastructure and Administrative Services;
- Strategic Aim 3: Realising eTransformation in Public Services;
- Strategic Aim 4: Enhancing Usage, Participation and Transparency.
- The developments in the scope of the 2016-2019 eGovernment Action Plan are summarised below:
 - The institutions carry out the process and method transformation studies to provide all the services as eGovernment services.
 - Electronic Document Management System is used in all central institutions.
 - MERSIS, which is a registry for businesses, is integrated into the eGovernment Gateway
 - Data dictionary studies have been started.
 - Services such as job search, employment, unemployment and retirement applications can be done via eGovernment Gateway.

- Certificate of inheritance interrogation can be obtained from the eGovernment Gateway.
- Many service steps for vehicle acquisition and registration have become available from the eGovernment Gateway. Efforts are underway to provide services in a holistic manner.
- Applications for the consumer arbitration committee can be made via eGovernment Gateway.
- A social media guide for public institutions was prepared and published in 2019.

In Turkey, A Digital Transformation Office of the Presidency was established to coordinate the digital transformation of public institutions. And The Ministry of Transport, and Infrastructure is responsible for the eGovernment Strategy and the Action Plan.

The portal <http://www.edevlet.gov.tr/> offers a means for participation and monitoring of the progress of the Action Plan and allows users and authorities to share announcements.

Tenth Development Plan (2014 - 2018)

The Tenth Development Plan (2014 - 2018) was approved at the 127th plenary session of the Grand National Assembly of Turkey, on 1 July 2013, in accordance with Law No. 3067, dated 30 October 1984. The Tenth Development Plan, covering the 2014 - 2018 period, was a milestone in advancing the society to high prosperity levels in line with 2023 targets. The Plan was prepared in a global economic environment with protracted risks, uncertainties, changes and transformations, with emerging and reshaping power balances among developed and developing economies.

The Tenth Development Plan was designed to include not only high, stable and inclusive economic growth, but also issues such as the rule of law, information society, international competitiveness, human development, environmental protection and sustainable use of resources. In the Plan, economic and social development processes of Turkey was discussed with a holistic and multi-dimensional view, and a participatory approach was adopted within the human-oriented development framework.

One of the objectives and policies of the plan was ‘Qualified People, Strong Society’, which included the title ‘eGovernment Applications in Public Services’. The main aim of the plan was to establish an eGovernment structure that provided services designed in accordance with user needs, including disadvantaged groups, in a user-oriented, collaborative, integrated and reliable manner through various platforms by ensuring personal data privacy and information security. This contributed to an effective, participative, transparent and accountable public administration. eGovernment activities were executed with an effective public management approach, and by a powerful coordinator authority, which will ensure strong management and coordination.

The required basic information systems for eGovernment service delivery were completed. Efforts to establish shared infrastructure and setting common standards continued. Common applications were expanded in the public sector, including local authorities. In this context, the completion of MERSİS, TAKBİS, Spatial Address Registration System

(MAKS), EKAP, the National Geographical Information System Infrastructure and Information Systems Disaster Management Centre projects was prioritised. Institutional eGovernment projects continued to be created within the framework of common action plans.

eGovernment applications and services will continue to be developed and integrated to the eGovernment Gateway. The distribution of the new eID card to all citizens were completed and the widespread use of eGovernment services were ensured. eCorrespondence Project, which provided an electronic environment for official correspondence among public agencies, was expanded. There were also issues regarding interoperability, mobile applications, eParticipation, sharing and re-using of public data.

eGovernment Gateway (e-Devlet Kapısı)

e-Devlet Kapısı, Turkey's eGovernment gateway (portal), was launched on 18 December 2008. The portal provides citizens and enterprises with a single point of access to eGovernment services. The gateway also serves a third group of users, the public sector agencies themselves, allowing them to interact with each other and exchange information. The contractor of the eGovernment Gateway is a governmental company Turksat, Turkey's main provider of satellite services and one of the biggest providers of IT infrastructure services.

As of June 2019, eGovernment Gateway had 4,808 services, 601 integrated organisations, and more than 42 million users. To ensure accessibility and user friendliness, the eGovernment Gateway is made accessible through the eGovernment Gateway call centre. The call centre, specifically designed for disabled people, started to operate for eGovernment related requests in 2018.

There are different information and articles on services that are given by e-Government Gateway and home portal links in Turkey.

1. Individuals and society: Access to information on topics such are homeless children, social assistance and solidarity, female gender issues, housing and gambling games.
2. Legal procedures, rights and defense: law measures, voter procedures, protection of the consumers, system of address registration, access to public notaries, application and required information.
3. Birth: Information and services such as birth registration, prenatal and post natal permits, maternal and infant health.
4. Military service and mobilization: Such procedures are military operation, officer ranks and reserve military, abroad or payment in foreign currency for military service.
5. Education: Kindergarten, primary and secondary schools, distance learning
6. Traffic: Traffic safety, motor vehicle operations, driving license procedures, highway control.
7. Health: Family health, public health, oral and dental health, nutrition information and scheduling appointments at hospital.

8. Citizens with disabilities: Health, education, employment, social rights and services, home-care services.
9. Turkish citizens living abroad: Information and services such as e-Consulate, population registrations, diploma equivalency, military service and marriage.
10. Art, culture and sport: Information and services such as cultural heritage, cultural activities, theatres, festivals, sport activities, fairs and local activities.
11. Job and career: Social Security Institution services for employees.
12. Family: Information and application forms for marriage, family health, population registration, children and teenagers and children rights.
13. Travel and tourism: General information about Turkey, types of tourism in Turkey, service for Turkish citizens living abroad, information about railway and highway transportation.

The actions carried out to promote the digitalisation of some social services:

- The Engelsiz Sağlık İletişim Merkezi project (ESİM), which provides 7/24 visual support in sign language, was put into service by the Ministry of Health in order to facilitate the access of the hearing-impaired citizens to health services and to eliminate the communication problems that may arise in the provision of health services. With the project, the citizens can immediately notify 112 Emergency Services via mobile applications that they can download to their personal phones free of charge, if they wish, they can start video calls or instant messaging. They can save serious time in emergency cases, where even seconds are very important. Thanks to the applications developed using the latest technology, they can report to 112 Emergency Services at the touch of a button, and send their location using GPS along with the notification, and send photos of the accident if they wish.
- With the service 'no barriers in e-Government Gateway' (e-devlette engel yok), the hearing-impaired citizens, who are users of e-Government Gateway, are able to get the call center service they need through mobile applications.

The services provided at the e-Government Gateway, whose number of users reaches 45 million, is increasing day by day, "When the type of e-Government-related service has become more widespread and all services become available from there, it can be provided services across the country to the citizens who do not have IT literacy or have disabilities. The hearing impaired citizens can download and use the Video Call Center Service application from application markets, and easily communicate with the operators on mobile devices using sign language or text. In addition, the citizens can easily access their questions, problems, requests and suggestions and they will be able to report and resolve them easily.

5. Conclusion: Digital need for social services

The social services sector has suffered major financial cuts in recent years, yet this sector is facing increasing economic needs in all European countries. In contrast, we are currently seeing a reduction in public budgets, yet the world's population is ageing. In this scenario, the digitalisation of social services can help to do more with fewer resources. The digitisation of social services has the potential to improve the quality of care and life of people who use these social services.

European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions released on April 2020 the report “Impact of digitalisation on social services”. It is apparent from this study that the initiatives of the EU and its member countries on the digitisation of health and social care focus primarily on health-related issues (e.g. electronic prescriptions or disease prevention). Actions related to the digitization of social services are often coordinated with healthcare, mainly focused on databases to share medical and social histories.

The main conclusions on the digitisation of social services in Europe are as follows:

- The use of robots is focused on the supervision of the elderly. These actions focus on:
 - > Cognitive tasks.
 - > Interaction between the robot and the eldest person.
 - > Help caregivers provide physical assistance (e.g. lift patients).

The use of robots in social assistance is limited by three fundamental factors:

1. High cost.
 2. Security issues.
 3. Opposition from caregivers and society at large.
- The use of the Internet of Things in social services will be helped in the future by the reduction of the costs of the devices and by the greater familiarity of the population with these technologies.
 - The use of AI in social services can be used for a variety of things:
 - > Plan resource management.
 - > Process applications for benefits in cash or in kind.
 - > Predict individual user needs.
 - > Help public employment services assign jobs to applicants more effectively.
 - The impact of the digitization of social services is limited, being in an initial phase of implementation. This digitization has positive and negative effects.
 - > Positive effects include:
 - Increases staff productivity.
 - Staff can spend more time on other tasks.
 - More efficient use of resources.
 - Avoid more expensive and intensive assistance.
 - Detect social services fraud.

- Digitization has allowed users to increase their perception of security of new technologies.
- > And the negative effects include increasing the workload, as staff need to spend more time informing, monitoring, or helping users unfamiliar with new technologies.
- There is resistance of staff and users of social services to digitization. The root cause of this resistance is a lack of knowledge and digital skills. Reducing this problem requires engaging users in the joint design of digitized social services.
- The main difficulties for the digital transformation of social services are:
 - > Fragmentation of social services.
 - > No institution responsible for the process of digitization of social services.
 - > Fragmentation of information in different databases.

If these problems were solving, the digitization process would be much easier.

Although the conclusions of the EUROFOUND report were made before the COVID-19 virus appeared, the findings are useful for policy makers in addressing the variety of issues that will arise after the pandemic. In general, digitization of social services can help reduce the risk of contagion and ensure continuity of care in times of confinement, confinement, and physical/social estrangement. Reducing the digital divide and investing in infrastructure and digital skills are crucial aspects, as these technologies are important tools to prevent contagion.

To complete these conclusions, the results obtained by the researchers who are experts in the digitalisation of social services are shown. First, the results obtained by Philip McCallion (School of Social Work, Temple University, Philadelphia) are shown:

In work around supports for independent living for people with intellectual/developmental disabilities, with colleagues and a provider I am looking at the use of navigation app using smart phone and a smart watch to both support adults with intellectual/developmental disabilities in independently travelling around their neighborhoods while offering real time connections to family and other caregivers so they may support these activities. We are looking at increasing community engagement, greater variety in community activities and greater confidence about community engagement in both the persons with intellectual/developmental disabilities and in their caregivers.

In my small regional city, I have seen how Facebook has become a primary means of community engagement and activism in the COVID-19 crisis. There are grassroots initiatives, such as Caremongering Groups and Sew the Curve (making cloth masks, scrub caps, etc.) that have sprung up to care for members of the community.

On the other hand, Silvia Straka (School of Social Work and Human Service, Thompson Rivers University) concludes that:

However, I see a disconnect between these grassroots initiatives and social work practice. Even in a technologically advanced country such as Canada, there are commonly low levels of technological literacy in terms of social work practice on the part of students, practitioners, and educators. We have not embedded these means into our practice and our education for practice.

The other disconnect I see is that over the years, we have seen a shift to clinical practice and a de-emphasizing of group and community practice (in the Global North). This leaves us without the theoretical and practice knowledge to engage with community at times such as these.

While I am excited about these grassroots initiatives, when they are not supported by existing agencies and/or social workers, I worry about the potential and risk for harm to vulnerable people. For example, volunteers helping seniors and single mothers of young children get groceries without an understanding of the risks of predators or people with very poor boundaries entering this picture concerns me. I love the volunteer and grassroots energy -- but I think as a field we need to think of our role in all this and how we can support and secure these initiatives (rather than take them over).

Finally, the contribution made by Mamia Tetvadze (Department of Marketing, Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University) is collected::

Epid-situation is forcing some institutes around the world to depend heavily on digital services. Such as - education, pharmacy and many other. „Non-essential" jobs is adapting and trying to be as competitive as they can.

Because of this in a small country like Georgia, Facebook, Zoom and Teams became vital applications to interact for academic and job purpose.

For example educational or career based institutes are using Zoom app. They are recording and saving it. For schools Georgia successfully uses Microsoft Teams. I think when this situation will be over, some of the companies and institutions will continue to use digital tools, to be more successful.

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